

Appendix for “Interpretable and Interactive Deep Survival Analysis with Time-dependent EXtreme Gradient Integration”

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APPENDIX

A. TCGA dataset baseline comparison

TABLE I: TCGA dataset baseline comparison

Baseline	C-index \uparrow
Zero-Vector (MB)	0.682
Random (RB)	0.708
Extreme (EB)	0.736

B. Mathematical Justification of the Attribution Smoothness Prior

a) *Total Variation (TV)*.: For a continuous $f(x)$,

$$\text{TV}(f) = \int |f'(x)| dx.$$

In discrete form, with attributions $\Phi = \{\phi_{i,l}^{(j)}\}$,

$$\Omega_{\text{smooth}}(\Phi) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{l=1}^p \sum_{j=1}^{T_{\max}-1} |\phi_{i,l}^{(j+1)} - \phi_{i,l}^{(j)}|.$$

b) *Optimization Objective*.:

$$\mathcal{L}(\Theta) = \underbrace{\sum_{j=1}^{T_{\max}} \sum_{i \in U_j} \ell(S_{\Theta}^{(j)}(X_i), Y_{i,j})}_{\mathcal{L}_{\text{pred}}} + \lambda_{\text{smooth}} \Omega_{\text{smooth}}(\Phi(\Theta, X)).$$

Under standard convexity assumptions, $\mathcal{L}_{\text{pred}}$ and Ω_{smooth} are convex in Φ , ensuring a unique global minimum.

c) *Bounded Variation*.: Requiring

$$\sum_{j=1}^{T_{\max}-1} |\phi^{(j+1)} - \phi^{(j)}| < \infty$$

guarantees attributions change gradually.

d) *Hyperparameter Settings*.: On TCGA data,

$$\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_{\text{smooth}} = 0.01$$

balances predictive performance (C-index) and attribution stability.

Fig. 1: Heatmap illustrating the sensitivity analysis of hyperparameters λ_1 and λ_2 on the C-index performance. Brighter areas indicate higher C-index values.

Fig. 2: Comparison of C-index performance under different values of the temporal smoothness hyperparameter λ_{smooth} . The results show that performance remains stable within a moderate range.

C. Computational Approach of TEXGI

a) *Discrete TEXGI*.: Given an extreme baseline $\tilde{X}_i^{(j)}$, sample a straight-line path

$$x_m = (1 - \alpha_m) \tilde{X}_i^{(j)} + \alpha_m X_i, \quad 0 = \alpha_0 < \dots < \alpha_M = 1.$$

With $\Delta x_{m,l} = x_{m,l} - x_{m-1,l}$, the l -th attribution at interval j is

$$\text{TEXGI}_l^{(j)} \approx \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{\partial f_{\theta_j}(x_m)}{\partial x_{m,l}} \Delta x_{m,l}.$$

Choosing $\tilde{X}_i^{(j)}$ from a generalized-Pareto tail forces the integral to traverse a high-risk region, producing interval-wise attributions that aggregate into a transparent, clinically focused explanation.

D. Effectiveness of Model Components Through Ablation Study

Ablation tests on eight datasets (NWTCO, GABS, METABRIC, FLCHAIN, CLT, CLV, Employee, SUPPORT)

TABLE II: Performance of Ablation Study Across Multiple Datasets for Deep Survival Model

Dataset	Baseline	+Dense	+Res	+Dense+Res	+Markov+Dense+Res
NWTCO (Test)	0.5720	0.5862	0.5991	0.6043	0.6261
GABS (Test)	0.5961	0.5908	0.6073	0.6205	0.6338
METABRIC (Test)	0.5901	0.5864	0.5986	0.6152	0.6233
FLCHAIN (Test)	0.6531	0.6971	0.7002	0.7205	0.7353
CLT (Test)	0.8324	0.8368	0.8412	0.8522	0.8570
CLV (Test)	0.8442	0.8501	0.8633	0.8725	0.8752
Employee (Test)	0.8677	0.8775	0.8901	0.9025	0.9065
SUPPORT (Test)	0.5246	0.5332	0.5651	0.5823	0.5890

isolate three add-ons—Dense Blocks, Residual Layers, Markov regularization. As Table II shows (C-index, test), Dense Blocks enhance feature interaction, Residual Layers let deeper nets learn stably, and the Markov term enforces smooth time-wise hazards; stacking all three delivers the best scores on every dataset, confirming each module’s complementary value.